

Brexit and the Lessons of the English Civil War in Kate Myers's *In Plain Sight*

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This paper examines literary representations of seventeenth-century Leicester in Kate Myers' *In Plain Sight* (2017). It argues that by deploying historical fiction, Myers reflects on current views regarding the UK's decision to leave the European Union. The paper maintains that the novel establishes an implicit historical analogy between the seventeenth-century English Civil War and Brexit. By creating such historical similarities, Myers tries to suggest that Brexit has been motivated not only by economic factors, but also by cultural ideas, namely Euroscepticism, English nationalism and anti-immigration attitudes. By showing the negative effects of the English Civil War on England and Europe's social and economic life, the author suggests that Brexit, in ways that are similar to the English Civil War, would lead to potential negative consequences on the economic, educational and health systems both in the UK and Europe. The paper contends that the novelist endeavours to undermine the British media's efforts to promote the "Leave" vote and urges people to appreciate multiculturalism and diversity and not to be swayed by the media's attempts to provoke ideas behind Brexit. Ultimately, Myers shows a solid stance against Brexit and warns against expected negative outcomes.

"Why, after so many years of tolerance?" (Myers 2018:14).

1. Introduction

Kate Myer was born and raised in Massachusetts, America. She was awarded her first Degree in English and Education in 1969 from Loyola University in New Orleans. She completed her post-graduate studies at Nottingham, an M.A. in American Studies and then moved to Leicester in 1972 as a part-time ESOL teaching. After that, she became a full-time teacher in a young offenders' institution. That was followed by teaching nearly twenty years in a local secondary school. Myers published a memoir, *Patchwork: An American Childhood* (2006), followed by several short stories in national magazines. In addition, she published a historical novel entitled *In Plain Sight*, which was published in 2017, a year after the Brexit Referendum. Currently,

Kate and her husband Bill live in Leicester (Myers, 2019).

In Plain Sight is set in seventeenth-century Leicester and tells the story of the historical figure, William Bentney, a Catholic Jesuit who is sent on the English mission. William endeavours to save his life and to maintain his faith as a Catholic during the English Civil War. He finds himself entrapped by the politics of London and thus decides to go to the city of Leicester, seeking refuge. In Leicester, he is welcomed by the Byerleys, a Roman Catholic family, residing at the Belgrave Hall. He spends forty years in the city where he enjoys a peaceful life. Ultimately, William is caught and confined to imprisonment. During his confinement in Leicester's gaol, William is treated humanely and is respected as an old learned Catholic chaplain. The novel ends with William's death after being afflicted with "Gaol Fever". While presenting the story of William, the novel depicts Leicester before and after the English Civil War and provides representations of the conflict between the Catholics and the Protestants following the English Reformation.

2. Brexit: the UK's decision to leave the EU and Literature

On June 23, 2016, the UK conducted polls to decide the future of its relationship with the EU. Unexpectedly, the "Leave" vote surpassed the "Remain" vote by a 51, 89 percent majority. Following the Brexit referendum, a number of newspaper articles established historical parallels between the seventeenth-century English Civil War and Brexit. For instance, Henderson (2016) argues that there are a set of striking similarities between the English Civil War of the 1640s and the 1650s and the Brexit vote. For him, the Civil War was triggered by difference in religious viewpoints and issues of sovereignty. He maintains that the economic factor also played a crucial role in provoking the war. As Henderson (2016) notes, those areas that supported the King during the Civil War are similar to those that voted for Brexit in the referendum of 2016. He maintains that the regions that supported the Parliament are akin to those that supported the "Remain" option. Henderson (2016) notes that "areas of industrial decline and cultural marginalization" voted for Brexit. According to him, understanding the causes and the outcomes of the Civil War may help in comprehending and predicting the consequences of Brexit. By the same token, Murin (2019) argues that, "at the time of the June 23rd, 2016 referendum we classified Brexit as having the same energy as the English Civil War in 1642-1651." As he notes, both incidents revolve around the sovereignty of Britain and show a split in attitudes and opinions regarding this issue. Hence, it is noted that the Brexit vote in 2016 provoked historical parallels with the English Civil War. This paper argues that in *In Plain Sight*, Myers creates historical analogies between the English Civil War and Brexit in order to reflect on contemporary conflicting views in this regard.

In response to the debates about the Brexit referendum in 2016, a number of literary works were published such as Ali Smith's *Autumn* (2016), Anthony Cartwright's *The Cut* (2017), and Mohsin Hamid's *Exit West* (2017). Young (2018:18) notes that in 2017, many post-Brexit literary accounts were submitted to the Man Booker Prize. Shaw names such accounts "BrexLit" and defines them as: "fictions that either directly respond or imaginatively allude to Britain's exit from the EU, or engage with the subsequent socio-cultural, economic, racial or cosmopolitical consequences of Britain's withdrawal" (2018:41-42). Through *In Plain Sight*, Myers contributes towards the growing BrexLit and the ongoing debates about Brexit. Nevertheless, unlike the other authors mentioned earlier, Myers deploys historical fiction to reflect on the present. In this regard, it becomes essential to mention George Lukács and Avrom Fleishman's views on historical fiction. Lukács argues: "The purpose of revisiting of the past is to enable fictional characters to cast a new light on the complexities of modern life at a fictional and temporal remove from the present" (1962: 38). According to Fleishman, by revisiting an earlier period of time, historical fiction can shed light on the present and deal with contemporary intricacies (1971:15). Put differently, the objective of historical fiction is not to represent the past for its sake; rather, it is meant to deal with contemporary matters. Furthermore, de Groot argues that a main function of the historical novel is to "challenge history" (2009:139). For him, "the historical novel fundamentally challenges subjectivities, offering multiple identities and historical story lines. Far from being a rigid, ordering structure, history seems to provide a set of potentialities and possibilities" (2009:139). Hence, historical fiction provides alternative narratives of history in ways that correspond to the author's political and ideological positions. Accordingly, though set in seventeenth-century England, *In Plain Sight* sheds light on a present issue, namely Brexit.

Discussing the role of literature in impacting the Brexit vote, Upstone argues in her book chapter entitled "Do novels tell us how to vote" that literature contributes towards shaping the world we live in. For her, literature is "potentially active player in the shaping of popular consciousness and the actions stemming from it" (2018:86). She further argues that a story has the ability to "shape ideas of diversity and tolerance in positive terms: that a story may, likewise, welcome you in and make you feel like you belong not only in that story, but in a place and in a community and in a nation" (2018:86). Thus, for her, literature plays a role in determining political outcomes, particularly the Brexit vote in this regard. Taking the abovementioned critics' arguments into consideration, it can be argued that Myers revisits the seventeenth-century with the objective of calling against the UK's decision of leaving the EU.

3. Britain and multiculturalism

Since the Brexit referendum in 2016, there has been a heating debate about the reasons behind the “Leave” vote. For Eaglestone (2018), Brexit is “an event in culture. Brexit grew from cultural beliefs, real or imaginary, about Europe and the UK.” Yet, Upstone argues that while dealing with the issue of Brexit, media focused on the economic facet and migration related issue but neglected the cultural side (2018:74). According to Shaw, the referendum reflected more than thirty years of Euroscepticism and rejection of migration from Europe and the Middle East (2018:39). In this regard, Mondal argues that Brexit has been motivated by imageries and ideologies inherited from Britain’s imperial past (2018:117). For him, Brexit was stirred by an “imperially nostalgic” nationalism that is rooted in a “structure of feeling” shaped by imperial ideologies and imaginaries (2018:120). As Mondal maintains, race is a basic component in this “structure of feeling”; while anti-EU immigration sentiment apparently seems to resist white immigrants, it is actually directed towards immigrants from different races: African, Middle Eastern, and Asian refugees (2018: 121-122). Hence, according to these critics, Brexit was not being driven by economic factors only but also by cultural ones, namely Euroscepticism, English nationalism and resistance to cultural diversity.

In this respect, NG argues in her book chapter entitled “Behind the Face of Terror” that in the aftermath of 9/11, there has been a shift from celebrating multiculturalism towards “suspicion and fear of immigrants” (2014:71-72). As she notes, in 2010, the German Chancellor Angela Merkel stated that politics of multiculturalism had failed. This declaration was followed by a statement by the British Prime Minister David Cameron in 2011 in which he claimed that policies of multiculturalism led to the escalation of terrorism (2014:71-72). Ashcroft and Bevir argue that the “resistance to multiculturalism contributed towards promoting Brexit” (2016:55). For them, “cultural pluralism was a clear cause of Brexit”. Most governmental policies between 1960-2000s encouraged integrity rather than assimilation, which resulted in a high degree of pluralism. The 9/11 attacks and the 7/7 bombings, which were followed by the “War on Terror” caused a backlash against Multiculturalism. Accordingly, Muslims have become “objects of public and governmental suspicion” (2016:55). Ashcroft and Bevir contend that some have seen minorities as a menace to the breakdown in social cohesion as they favour their personal interests over civil loyalties (2016:55). On this subject, Fitzgerald and Smoczyński argue that the British media played a crucial role in presenting immigrants as the “Other” and as a threat to the UK economy, security, National Health system, education, and benefits (2015: 341). In light of these critics’ arguments about Brexit, it can be argued that Myers, by means of historical analogy, suggests that Brexit has been motivated by anti-immigration views according to which immigrants are seen as a menace to the UK economy as well as by cultural ideas, particularly, Euroscepticism, English nationalism and anti-

multiculturalism attitudes.

As can be noticed, the novel provides depictions of the seventeenth-century Protestant-Catholic conflict in England following the Reformation and during the ensuing Civil War. Literary representation of this religious and political tension is highly suggestive as it is meant to represent contemporary division of the British community with regard to the UK being a member of the EU. In view of that, it becomes essential to discuss the conflicting views about European integration from the perspectives of Catholicism and Protestantism. Nelson and Guth argue that two attitudes towards Europe, which have their roots in the Reformation of the sixteenth century, have emerged following WWII. The first vision is based on the belief that the ideal Europe looks like a "single people in a federal state" (2015:16-17). The second vision sees the ideal Europe as an "international organization" (2015:16-17). They maintain that whilst the Catholics support European integration, the Protestants have the tendency towards resisting it (2015:16-17). Drawing upon Nelson and Guth's arguments and my reading of the novel, the paper argues that the novelist deploys the Catholic-Protestant clash to set up historical similarities between this historical conflict and the contemporary contradictory views about Brexit. Thus, the Catholics in the novel represent anti-Brexit stance whereas the Protestants denote pro-Brexit position. Accordingly, William, as a Catholic Jesuit that is on a mission supervised by the Catholic Church in Rome, represents ideas of European integrity and multiculturalism whereas Protestantism represents British Euroscepticism and resistance to immigration and cultural pluralism. William goes through hardships, trying to maintain his Catholic faith. He is pursued by the Protestant and finally is put in prison where he catches "Gaol Fever" and dies. Such representations, through historical analogies, are used to suggest that anti-EU attitudes and Euroscepticism have been promoting Brexit.

4. The role of the media in promoting Brexit

In the novel, in order to escalate the tension between the Catholics and the Protestants, the "Popish Plot" is prepared. As the reader learns, the conspiracy is planned by Titus Oates, a Protestant Minister, and Israel Tone. Oates fabricates the news that the Catholics are plotting against King Charles II and are planning to assassinate him in order to replace him with his brother James. Finally, it is revealed that the news was made-up by Oates; accordingly, he is imprisoned. As the narrator says, "Seventeen new newspapers sprang up. There were poems, broadsides, cartoons, bawdy songs, ballads, all featuring some grotesque Catholic menace foisted on the good British public by the King" (Myers 2017:72). As we learn, variable means of communications, available back then, are utilized to promote the conspiracy. According to the narrator: "Titus Oates'

allegations resulted in the arrest of five Catholic noblemen, Jesuit priests and lay men and women associated with them. Priests were fleeing back to France (Myers 2017:73). As can be concluded, the conspiracy is planned to provoke anti-Catholic sentiment. Such representations of the plot allude to the role of the contemporary media in promoting division and conflicts.

Bijsmans (2016) argues in “Brexit, ‘the Media’ and the Illusive Nature of Euroscepticism” that the British Press played a role in misinterpreting European politics and promoting an anti-European stance. However, he contends that this tendency did not only appear following Brexit; rather it preceded Brexit and it is well-documented (2018:133). In this regard, Bickerton contends that “critics of the British Press believe it has fueled a nationalistic anti-Europeanism” (2018:133). Ridge-Newman et al. argue that the media played a significant role in deploying the issue of migration for political objectives. The issue of the migrants was broadcast in alignment with the debate about Britain’s position in the EU. Thus, immigration was used as a convincing tool to orient the vote in the referendum (2018:41-42). They maintain that the media represented the 2016 referendum as a democratic opportunity to decide the immigration issue. This way of dealing with the migration topic is a continuation of existing media tendency to represent immigrants as “separate from a community” (2018:41-42). For them, immigrants were voiceless and spoken on their behalf (2018:41-42). In this respect, Esses et al., argue that the media had a significant role in shaping discourse and policies regarding immigrants and refugees (2013:520). They maintain that the media represented immigrants and refugees as a menace to the host society (2013:531). From the above accounts, it can be concluded that the British media played a key role in promoting the notion that immigrants, whether from Europe, Africa, or the Middle East, pose a threat to the UK economy and social security. Thus, it can be argued that Myers provides horrendous representations of the outcome of the conspiracy to show that inadequate and false sources of information are a means of intensifying the tension between the Catholics and the Protestants during the English Civil War. She attempts through, historical parallels, to suggest that the British media contributed towards promoting Euroscepticism, which consequently encouraged the “Leave” vote. Ultimately, she warns British people of being swayed by the British media’s attempts to promote such a notion.

5. Migrants and the UK Economy

In the novel, Joseph is a young man who is skeptic about his faith and who appears convinced about the idea that being a Catholic hinders his financial progress. He believes that William’s presence puts his interest in danger. Joseph feels that William is an outsider and describes him as “the interfering old” who hampers his economic progress. For Joseph, getting rid of William would help

the former get better economic chances in life. According to the narrator, “The more he thought about it, the more he was convinced that the Jesuit was the stumbling block in his life. Get rid of him and his life was full of possibilities. Let him be hunted down, put him under threat” (Myers 2017: 77). Joseph believes that after expelling William, “a world of career opportunities would open for him” (Myers 2017:77). Thus, William represents immigrants who are perceived as a hamper to British youth seeking job opportunities and better economic and social conditions in the UK. Joseph’s view of William as an outsider who poses a threat to the future of the young people in Leicester is meant to represent the contemporary British anti-immigration stance which is based on the belief that immigration affects the UK economy negatively. Through the character of Joseph, Myers implies that British youth are swayed by the idea that immigrants threaten the UK economy, which ultimately breeds anti-immigration attitudes and promotes the “Leave” vote.

In an attempt to defy the media’s efforts in this respect, Myers presents William as an asset rather than a source of danger to his community. William is constructed in the novel as a peaceful and productive character. As the narrator tells us, “He was no threat to anyone” (Myers, 2017: 13-14). The narrator goes on to say: “He was no threat. A kindly, educated old man who had many friends in town made a pleasant change from their usual charges” (Myers 2017:101). In addition, during William’s confinement, the narrator says: “He’d have his own space, and he’d be allowed his books and small table and stool. He had thought of keeping a diary or creating a book of meditations on his confinement” (Myers 2017:102). Furthermore, the narrator informs us: “He was more like Leicester’s gaol’s chaplain in residence than its prisoner” (Myers, 2017: 116). Thus, William appears as a learned, cultured man who is able to establish healthy friendships with his surrounding and to contribute towards the diversity of the neighborhood. In addition, as the narrator says, William starts his own project in Leicester, which indicates that he is productive and financially independent. William is presented as an asset rather than a threat to his community. Such images of William, by means of historical analogy, are meant to defy the contemporary British media’s attempt to present immigrants as a burden on the UK’s economy and as a menace to Britain’s social security. Ultimately, the author undermines ideas behind anti-immigration attitudes and Euroscepticism.

6. The Consequences of Brexit

With the objective of suggesting that Brexit would negatively impact the economic, the social, and the educational life in the UK, Myers presents the negative influence of the seventeenth-century English Civil War on the life in England. In *Palin Sight* offers representations of Leicester before and after the Civil War. This division is highly significant as Myers tries to show that the

Civil War left a negative impact on the living conditions in Leicester.

Martill and Staiger note that Britain's withdrawal from the EU would influence the political, juridical, and economic life (2018:1). They contend that such impact will extend from "immigration policy to agriculture subsidies, criminal justice measures to environmental standards, financial services regulations to nuclear power technology, university student fees to employment laws and aviation" (2018:1). For them Brexit "requires rethinking and re-legislating a vast number of policy areas" (2018:1). On the day following the Brexit referendum in 2016, Krugman, the Nobel-Prizewinning and Professor of Economics at Princeton University and London School of Economics, stated that "Britain will become less productive" and that "Brexit will make Britain poorer" (2016). Kierzenkowski et al., argue that Brexit will have a vast negative impact on the UK's economy and will create uncertainty about the future of Europe. They maintain that if the UK decided to stay, the living standards of Europe, including the UK, would be boosted (2016:5).

In the novel, the narrator informs the reader that the living conditions in Leicester were better before the war: "They were lucky. That was back in 1641, before the Civil War wreaked havoc on Leicester" (Myers 2017: 9-10). Thus, the narrator indicates that the Civil War was a setback for Leicester's economy. Moreover, the war and the change in the way England is governed created a state of uncertainty regarding the economy. The narrator goes on to tell us that the family's trade business has been negatively influenced by the war: "The wool trade in Leicester and the Byerleys' business, while profitable enough, now seemed well in decline. He secretly wondered how secure their future might be" (Myers, 2017: 25). The narrator continues: "He too was anxious, trade was very slow. No one wants to place orders with the future so certain (Myers 2017: 35). Commenting on the consequences of the war on trade we learn that, "Trade was very slow. No one wants to place orders with the future so uncertain. Can't trust getting payment, can't risk moving goods from the warehouse" (Myers 2017:35). Describing the situation following the start of the war, the narrator says: "Now nothing felt safe or secure" (Myers 2017:72). In light of what the narrator indicates about the life in Leicester before and after the Civil War, it is clear the novelist endeavours to show that the Civil War left a negative impact on the economic conditions of the city and created a state of uncertainty about the future. Historically speaking, Coates argues that the English Civil War "led to a major crisis in England's worldwide trade" (2004:256). It can be noted that the author adheres to what the historical record provides about the outcomes of the Civil War. Hence, it can be argued that such representations of the aftermath of the war are meant, through historical similarities, to suggest that the UK's decision to leave the EU would result in nothing but creating economic complexities and a state of insecurity. Hence, one can argue that through historical parallel, the author tries to warn against

expected negative economic outcomes of Brexit.

Myers presents the impact of the Civil War on education in general and on women's education in particular. Informing the reader about the complexities Catholic families face trying to find proper education for their offspring, the narrator says: "The son had to escape abroad to finish his studies in a Catholic college" (Myers 2017:53). The author tries to show that the Civil War hindered the educational process in England and created complexities for the Catholic students. In this respect, it was indicated that following the 2016 Referendum, "there are roughly 125000 non-UK, EU students enrolled on degree courses in the UK, paying domestic fees and eligible for student loans, fees, application process, and visa requirements (EU students: how would Brexit affect you studying in the UK?, 2016). Thus, it was expected that the whole teaching process and scientific research will be impacted by Brexit. Through such representations, the author suggests that Brexit would hamper EU students' education. By presenting the potential harmful aftermath of Brexit on education, Myers calls for reconsidering the UK's decision of leaving the EU.

Moreover, the author depicts the influence of the English Civil War on Women's education. Expressing the difficulties that she faces while trying to get proper education in England in the aftermath of the Civil War, Rebecca says: "I want to find a way to maintain my freedom, stay in England, keep my faith and pursue an education for myself and other like-minded women, and not just affluent ones" (Myers 2017:65). Hence, Rebecca represents the adverse impact of the Civil War on women's education. By means of historical parallels, the author provides undesirable depictions of the potential consequences of Brexit on women's education in particular. According to the historical record, Fraser contends that during the Reformation, "the disappearance of the convent" deprived English girls of having a proper access to education. For the purpose of receiving education, a number of Catholic families sent their daughters abroad (1984: 214-215). Thus, following the Civil War, Catholic women's chances of getting proper education were reduced. It can be noted that the author deploys such historical information about the Civil War to represent the potential impact of Brexit on women's education in her novel. In the present time, Gil (2019) notes that, "the EU currently provides vital protection for the most marginalised students including women". Thus, it can be argued that Brexit jeopardises marginalised women's rights to education. Through creating historical similarities between the seventeenth-century English Civil War and contemporary Brexit, the novelist suggests that Brexit would harm the educational process in the UK and Europe and would be a menace to some women's access to education.

Furthermore, the novel shows the adverse effects of the Civil War on health services in England. The narrator informs us: "Within four years the capital would be struck down by plague" (Myers 2017:61). The reader is also

informed that “the thought of plague, a recurring nightmare which attacked Leicester about every ten years, was enough to panic the authorities” (Myers 2017: 87). According to Porters (1996), as a result of the English Civil War, the income of hospitals was reduced due to the economic circumstances. In addition, there was a number of wounded soldiers and prisoners; charitable giving declined and deaths caused by plague were increasing (192-193). In the present time, McHale (2019) argues that since a figure of £ 35 million appeared on a bus during the referendum in 2016, there has been a controversial debate about the NHS. McHale contends that there would be potential risks if the UK decided to leave the EU. She provides some examples of such jeopardies. For instance, the cross-collaboration and cooperation between the EU and the UK will be hindered and accordingly the UK citizen would not be able to have a free or reduced cost access to the European Health Insurance. Another example is that children in the border areas between Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland in need of cardiac surgery would be sent to hospitals in Dublin instead of being transferred to a hospital in Northern Ireland, which consequently puts patients’ care in danger. Taking the aforementioned accounts into consideration, the paper argues that Myers deploys historical analogy to indicate that Brexit would lead to negative consequences regarding the health system both in the UK and Europe.

7. Representations of Leicester as a multicultural, multifaith city

In the novel, the author endeavours to depict the seventeenth-century Leicester as a tolerant, multi-faith city. William as a Catholic priest seeks asylum in Leicester after being pursued by the Protestants. He joins the Byerley family who welcomes him warmly in Belgrave Hall. William spends peaceful and productive time in Leicester where he starts his business. As the narrator indicates, “Leicester, by and large, let people be. Religious toleration was more generally welcomed than in most of the country” (Myers 2017:11). Furthermore, the narrator informs the reader how Leicester is perceived from the perspective of the characters: “Once she arrives in the city Rebecca senses that the surrounding neighborhood is friendly” (Myers 2017:12). Moreover, the narrator indicates that the city is a hospitable place that welcomes people regardless of their background: “Throughout the twelve days all levels of society would be welcomed into the Great Hall, with set days for different groups, local villagers and tenanted farmers and the miller, another day for business associates, another extended family, including their grand cousins” (Myers 2017:29). Hence, the narrator draws a picture of a harmonious Leicester where people of different faiths and social backgrounds can coexist peacefully. Even after he is arrested and imprisoned in Leicester, William is treated respectfully and humanely at Leicester’s gaol. According to the narrator, “He

had been arrested and placed in Leicester's gaol. Leicester did not want to lose their prize so he was kept secure with multiple sets of shackles and was closely guarded" (Myers 2017:87). Despite the fact that William does not embrace "the national" religion of England, the people of Leicester are happy to offer him peaceful and calm residence among them.

Instead of being treated harshly as a prisoner, William "was more like Leicester's gaol's chaplain in residence than its prisoner" (Myers 2017:116). By the same token, talking about his experience in Leicester's gaol, William sates: "I was trusted, and I might even say, befriended." (Myers 2017:158). Commenting on the same issue Richard, the sheriff of Leicester, says: "Leicester will look after you and keep you safe from harm" (Myers 2017: 159). Following his displacement to Derby, the narrator informs us that: "Bentney longed to return to the tolerance he'd found in Leicester" (Myers 2017:144). As can be noticed in the novel, the "peace-loving-folk" of Leicester endeavours to protect the Catholic William against the aggressions of the Protestant. Clearly, Myers attempts to present Leicester as a city that welcomes cultural pluralism and appreciates difference. Such images of Leicester are meant to reflect on ideas of multiculturalism in our present time, particularly with regard to ongoing debates about Brexit.

Regarding contemporary Leicester, the city proved to be a symbol of multiculturalism. For instance, the first Islamic centre was founded in Leicester in 1986. The institute was built by a group of Pakistani Muslims and is considered now as the oldest mosques in Leicester. (Leicester Council of Faiths /Working with faith communities in Leicester: n.d.) In another statement, it is indicated that the Leicester council has been operating since 1986. Since then, it has been playing a significant role in promoting tolerance and peaceful coexistence among the different religious minorities. The council's members consist of city's Bahá'ís, Buddhists, Christians, Hindus, Jains, Jews, Muslims and Sikhs. The activities of the council contributed towards a multi-faith, tolerant Leicester (Leicester Council of Faiths /Working with faith communities in Leicester: n.d.). In addition, according to Hall et al., a group of researchers from the London School of Economics and Political Sciences, Narborough Street in Leicester has been labelled as one of super-divers streets in the UK (2015:2). Moreover, for Brown (2010), "Leicester will soon become the first British city with a non-white majority – a transformation which is welcomed by its citizens". Most importantly, it was stated that Leicester voted "Remain" in EU, Referendum, 2016 (Leicester City Council/ EU Referendum 2016, 2016). Accordingly, the paper contends that the author endeavours to depict Leicester as a tolerant, welcoming place in order to present contemporary Leicester as a multicultural, multi-faith city. In an email between the author and I, Myers expressed her fascination with Leicester when she first moved to the city as an immigrant fifty years ago. She was glad that she could be herself while

embracing other cultures. She told her experience learning from her students in Leicester to wear the Sari. She also encouraged her students to “welcome, not to intimidate” (2019). Myers also expressed her admiration for the different cultural and religious activities that take place in the city such as Diwali, Eid Prayers and the Caribbean carnival. Furthermore, she manifested her appreciation for Muslim women’s efforts of conducting charity activities in the city (2019). In addition, the author mentions in the Afterword of the novel that the present Belgrave Hall, which is the main setting of the novel, is situated in Loughborough Road in Leicester and owned by Sri Jeya Durga Temple. For her, this reflects the diverse nature of Leicester city. It can be noted that the author’s standpoint of multiculturalism in the novel is akin to hers in the correspondence (Myers 2019).

Towards the end of the novel, William says: “Can we pray together to the same God we both believe in? We can pray for His understanding and His mercy” (Myers 2017:176). William’s words are very significant as they are a call for embracing cultural pluralism, multi-faith and tolerance. Furthermore, his words can be read as the author’s call for appreciating multiculturalism. Myers urges people to reconsider the “Leave” vote and calls for supporting multiculturalism and cultural diversity. Ultimately, she shows a solid anti-Brexit stance and warns against the harmful consequences of Brexit.

8. Conclusion

As it has been argued in this paper, Myers deploys the historical conflict between the Catholics and the Protestants following the sixteenth-century English Reformation and the ensuing English Civil War to reflect on the ongoing debates about the Brexit. She uses the historical character of William Bentney, a Catholic Jesuit, to represent ideas of multiculturalism and plurality. Nevertheless, she deploys Protestantism to represent Euroscepticism and anti-immigration stances. The paper maintains that by establishing historical analogies between the seventeenth-century English Civil War Brexit, the author suggests that Brexit has been motivated by cultural ideas particularly, English nationalism and Euroscepticism. Moreover, the author shows that the British media has played a crucial role in promoting such notions. By showing the negative consequences of the English Civil War in the novel, the novelist suggests that the UK’s decision of leaving the EU would leave adverse impact on the UK economy as well as on the educational and the health systems. For this objective, Myers presents the complexities that the city of Leicester faced in the aftermath of the English Civil War. In addition, the novelist depicts seventeenth-century Leicester as a diverse and multi-faith city where people live peacefully and accommodate refugees. By means of such representations, Myers calls for embracing multiculturalism, diversity and peaceful coexistence.

Ultimately, she warns against the consequences of Brexit and shows profound anti-Brexit stance.

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